

Assessment of Knowledge and Awareness about HIV/AIDS among students of Sherubtse College (SC)

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Abstract

Increasing number of HIV/AIDS cases every year in the country is a concern for everybody. Despite the national concern and various awareness campaigns organized on HIV/AIDS, the number of HIV cases is steadily on rise since its detection in the country. Therefore, the main aim of this study was to assess the knowledge and awareness on HIV/AIDS among the students of Sherubtse College (SC) as well as to see whether gender, age level and qualification level has any relationship. So, a cross-sectional study was conducted among 150 voluntary students of Arts and Humanities, BSc. Life Sciences and Social Sciences Students. A stratified sampling was taken for data collection. The data were collected by administering 20 true-false items on the spot. The data were analyzed using excel sheet (2007). The study revealed that majority of the students has poor knowledge and awareness on HIV/AIDS. Gender-wise, male indicated better knowledge and awareness against female participants. These findings indicated that an awareness programme on HIV/AIDS needs to be conducted.

Key words: HIV/AIDS, awareness, students, stratified sampling, HIV-KQ 18 & HIV- KQ 45, Sherubtse College.

Introduction

AIDS (acquired immunodeficiency syndrome) caused by HIV (human immuno-deficiency virus) has become one of the world's most serious health and development challenges since its detection in 1981. There are approximately 36.7 million people living with HIV in the world of which 5.1 million are in Asia and The Pacific and 1.1 million people have died in 2015.

In Bhutan, the first case of HIV was detected in 1993, and the number of cases increased from the year 2000 onwards, with more than 80% of the total cases reported within the last 10 years despite the early establishment of National HIV/AIDS and STI Control Programme. Bhutan is one of the few countries in South Asia that continues to experience a low adult (15-49 years) HIV prevalence. Geographically, HIV cases have been detected in 18 out of the 20 districts. Towns in the bordering districts with India have been reported with higher cases of HIV infections. As of June 2016, Bhutan has the total reported cases of 492 out of which 51 percent are male and 49 percent female. 86 HIV patients have died and currently 386 people are living with HIV/AIDS in the country of which 34 are children.

Globally, it is known that there is a lack of HIV knowledge among youth between the ages of 15-24. The World Health Organization states that youths are at the epicenter for preventing the progression of the HIV/AIDS pandemic (WHO, 2004). The WHO estimates that youths ages 15 to 24 comprise 50% of all new HIV infections and consequently must be targeted for education in decreasing transmission and reducing the stigmatization of an HIV diagnosis (WHO, 2004). Young people in this age-group are at particularly high risk of HIV infection from unprotected sex, sex between men and IV drug-use because of the very high prevalence rates often found amongst people who engage in these behaviors. Young people are also often especially vulnerable to exploitation that may increase their susceptibility to infection.

In Bhutan also, the reported cases of HIV infections are mostly the young age groups who are sexually active. Since there is no cure for HIV/AIDS, prevention is the only best way to protect from this disease. The awareness degree and related factors of people vary on age, education, gender, socioeconomic status, well organized health-care and support activities (Adkins, 2002). It is important that concerted attempts should be performed for sexually active young individuals, through educational and occupational programs to inform them of sexually transmitted diseases (Uwakwe, 2000; Hou, 2009). For effective prevention and protection from HIV/AIDS, the level of knowledge and awareness among the young population is very important.

Therefore, this research was designed to find out the answers for the following questions:

- *How knowledgeable and aware are the students on HIV/AIDS in SC?*
- *Who has better knowledge on HIV/AIDS (male or female)?*
- *What kind of correlation exists between qualification level and knowledge/awareness of the students?*

Materials and methods

A cross-sectional survey was conducted in October 2017 using self-administered questionnaires among students. Students were informed about the purpose of the study. The students who volunteered to participate were given the set of questionnaire to complete. Students were informed not discuss answers with their friends. The completed questionnaires were retrieved immediately after the sessions.

Samples were purposively selected to include equal numbers of students by gender and year of enrolment. In this study, the data were collected from first year to third year Department of Arts and Humanities, Bsc. Life Sciences and Social Sciences. From each level, 30 participants with equal gender were selected. In total, 150 students took part in survey.

Data were collected and knowledge was assessed using 20-item self-administered anonymous questionnaire adapted from HIV Knowledge questionnaire (HIV-KQ-18) developed by Carey, M. P., & Schroder, K. E. E. (2002). The knowledge questions were assessed using the key. Each right answer was given a score of 1 while a wrong or don't know response was scored 0. Total knowledge scores ranged between 0-20.

Survey questionnaire used for data collection:

I. Demographic information

Put a tick against whichever is appropriate to you.

1. **Gender:** Male Female Third gender

2. **Age (completed years):**

3. **Course:**

Arts and Humanities I year

BSc. Life Sci II year

Social Sci III year

Computer Sci II year

Physical Sci I Year

II. For each statement, please circle “True” (T), “False” (F), or “I don’t know” (DK). If you do not know, please do not guess; instead, please circle “DK.”

Sl. No.	Items	True	False	I don't know
1	HIV and AIDS are the same thing.	T	F	DK
2	AIDS is the cause of HIV.	T	F	DK
3	Coughing and sneezing DO NOT spread HIV.	T	F	DK
4	A person can get HIV by sharing a glass of water with someone who has HIV.	T	F	DK
5	Pulling out the penis before a man climaxes/ cums keeps a woman from getting HIV during Sex.	T	F	DK
6	A woman can get HIV if she has anal sex with a man.	T	F	DK
7	Showering, or washing one's genitals/private parts, after sex keeps a person from getting HIV.	T	F	DK
8	All pregnant women infected with HIV will have babies born with AIDS.	T	F	DK

9	People who have been infected with HIV quickly show serious signs of being infected.	T	F	DK
10	There is a vaccine that can stop adults from getting HIV.	T	F	DK
11	People are likely to get HIV by deep kissing, putting their tongue in their partner's mouth, if their partner has HIV.	T	F	DK
12	A woman cannot get HIV if she has sex during her period.	T	F	DK
13	There is a female condom that can help decrease a woman's chance of getting HIV.	T	F	DK

14	A natural skin condom works better against HIV than does a latex condom.	T	F	DK
15	A person will NOT get HIV if she or he is taking antibiotics.	T	F	DK
16	Having sex with more than one partner can increase a person's chance of being infected With HIV.	T	F	DK
17	Taking a test for HIV one week after having sex will tell a person if she or he has HIV.	T	F	DK
18	A person can get HIV by sitting in a hot tub or a swimming pool with a person who has HIV.	T	F	DK
19	A person can get HIV from oral sex.	T	F	DK
20	HIV can be spread by mosquitoes.	T	F	DK

Results

The overall knowledge score of the participants on HIV/AIDS was 55.10% with a range of minimum score 1 to maximum of 19. Average score by male and female was 58.27% and 51.93% respectively. 33.33% of the total student (n=150) scored less than 50, 22.67% scored between 50-60, 18.67% scored between 60-70, 18% scored between 70-80, 6.67% scored between 80-90 and only 0.67% of the total student scored 90-100.

Gender Vs average score

Some of the specific findings during the survey are:

- 71% responded incorrectly-AIDs is the cause of HIV
- 75% responded incorrectly-All pregnant women infected with HIV will have babies born with AIDS.
- 70.67% responded correctly-There is a female condom that can help decrease a woman's chance of getting HIV
- 96.57% responded incorrectly-A natural skin condom works better against HIV than does a latex condom.

- 90.67% responded correctly-Having sex with more than one partner can increase a person's chance of being infected with HIV
- 76% responded incorrectly-Taking a test for HIV one week after having sex will tell a person if she or he has HIV.
- 74.67% responded correctly-People who have been infected with HIV quickly show serious signs of being infected.

- 86.67% responded incorrectly-A person can get HIV from oral sex.

Discussions

The average score was 55.10% (n=150) indicating the level of knowledge and awareness is just satisfactory. 56% of the total sample had poor to satisfactory knowledge and awareness. 44% of the total sample had good to very good knowledge and awareness. Males (57.17%) had better knowledge and awareness as compared to females (52.43%). Performance level increased with the qualification level. IV year (52.5%) had lower performance as compared to II year (54.8%) and III year (58.7%).

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